

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Linguistics, linguoculturology, applied linguoculturology, teaching of Russian linguistics, linguistics, linguodidactics.

Introduction.

Today it has become obvious that in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, it is not enough to teach students vocabulary and grammar. Russian communication will become impossible without the student mastering the key points of Russian culture. That is why improving the study of the most important components of Russian culture by students in the process of teaching the Russian Language is relevant.

Modern linguoculturology, acting as a specific phenomenon in the science of language, positions itself as a continuation of the work of a number of researchers of the past. These are such well-known researchers as V.Humboldt, A.A.Potebnya, E.Sepir, B.Wharf [Humboldt, 1984; Potebnya, 1999; Sepir, 1993; Wharf, 1960]. However, we believe it would be a stretch to combine the names of these researchers around the idea of the connection between

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF APPLIED LINGUOCULTUROLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6692144>

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the problems of theory and practice of modern applied linguoculturology, its obvious advantages, disadvantages and possible prospects, the analysis of the theory and terminology used in this direction, as well as the results of its application in the practice of teaching RUSSIAN AS FOREIGN

language and culture. Actually, it is about this formulation (the connection of language and culture) that we can speak only based on the conclusions made by V. Humboldt. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the scientific background on which V. Humboldt worked was very productive and fertile. The end of the XVIII – beginning of the XIX century in Germany there was an incredible rise in humanitarian knowledge. Indo-European studies, psycholinguistics, and the study of languages and cultures of the peoples of equatorial Africa and Southeast Asia developed in the field of linguistics.

The Russian-Ukrainian background of the humanities of A.A.Potebnya's time was not distinguished by such richness and diversity (in Russia at that time, the ideas of Slavic unity and Missianism of the Russian Empire prevailed among the creative intelligentsia), which was clearly reflected in his research. According to the

ideas of A.A.Potebni, culture, being a phenomenon of a higher order than language, has a direct influence on language. Meanwhile, A.A.Potebnya did not provide obvious evidence of such an influence, which can be explained by the early stage of the development of Russian linguistics.

Anyway, V. Humboldt and A.A.Potebnya worked at the level of general theory. Representing the German humanities of his time, V. Humboldt was a stronger theorist than A.A. Potebnya.

Unlike A.A.Potebni, according to the Sepir-Whorf hypothesis of linguistic relativity, the national language has a special structure that influences the national culture. Despite the fact that Sepir-Whorf's research is already a modern science, they are rightly criticized for the weakness of the evidence base and the excessive breadth of conclusions.

Thus, if we consider a kind of extract from the ideas of V. Humboldt, A.A.Potebni, E. Sepir and B. Whorf, it turns out that these ideas often contradict each other, do not reveal the essence of the interaction of language and culture, and in general, represent completely heterogeneous research worlds.

If we search for the predecessors of modern Russian linguoculturology, then with some reservations we can focus on the methods of the so-called Prague Linguistic Circle, whose members considered the national language not as an integrity, but as a differentiated structure. This differentiation, in their opinion, is based on subcultures of various social strata and social groups. Of course, the members of the Prague Linguistic Circle did not try to build any coherent linguistic and cultural theory, since they never set themselves the

task of describing the interaction of language and culture.

Meanwhile, in the case of the Prague Linguistic Circle, we can talk about the formation of the methodological base of linguoculturology, in particular, about the research of living processes in language. "Specific facts of culture are reflected in some specific levels of language, primarily in vocabulary, partly in stylistics" [Gavranek, 1967: 44]. This conclusion can certainly be accepted as the most important theoretical one for linguoculturology.

Russian Russian is methodologically closest to the Prague Linguistic Circle of the modern school of the V.V.Vinogradov Institute of the Russian Language of the Russian Academy of Sciences, whose staff, for the most part, are engaged in the study of the Russian language within the framework of traditional directions, including the study of living processes in the language.

In this sense, the definitions of linguoculturology as a direction of Russian studies are of interest, since the existing definitions imply an understanding or misunderstanding by linguoculturologists of the main tasks of this direction.

The main definition here is V.V.Vorobyov: "Linguoculturology is a complex scientific discipline that studies the relationship and interaction of culture and language in its functioning" [Vorobyov, 1993: 47]. T.V.Evsyukova writes that linguoculturology is "the development of the problem of the correlation of language and culture" [Evsyukova, 2005. P. 4]. V.N.Telia considers linguoculturology as "a part of ethnolinguistics, which is devoted to the study and description of the correspondence of language and culture in

their synchronous interaction" [Telia, 1996: 216-217].

According to V.A.Maslova, "the object of linguoculturology is the study of the interaction of language, which is a translator of cultural information, culture with its attitudes and preferences and the person who creates this culture using language. The object is located at the junction of several fundamental sciences – linguistics and cultural studies, ethnography and psycholinguistics" [Maslova, 2011: 36]. N.N.Ivanova writes that "the object of the study of linguoculturology is the system-structural relations that have developed under the influence of the culture of linguistic society" [Ivanova, 2005: 4].

In other words, it gives the impression of some kind of misunderstanding by the researchers themselves of the actual subject and object of research. The ambiguity of thought is hidden behind the balancing of terms. In fact, researchers are talking either about some cultural phenomena, trying to project them into language, or about the facts of language, trying to tie them to specific facts of culture, thereby reproducing the contradiction of the ideas of A.A.Potebni and E. Sepir (language affects culture - culture affects language). At the same time, this impression is formed not only by us. Thus, T.V.Evsyukova notes that the subject and object of linguoculturology fluctuates at the present stage, i.e. it does not have a uniform understanding even among narrow specialists. "Either linguistic facts that can say something about culture are analyzed, or some cultural phenomena that are reflected in language are investigated" [Evsyukova, 2005]. The validity of T.V.Evsyukova's analysis and our

observations on this matter seem to be correct not only from the ambiguity of the subject of linguoculturology research, but also from the very stylistics of this direction: despite the obvious fact of the interaction of language and culture, the ambiguity and streamlining of formulations in almost all parts of research in the field of linguoculturology indicates insufficient elaboration of the scientific foundations of the direction itself.

There is no doubt that linguoculturology as a direction will continue to develop. The paradox of modern linguoculturology is based on the fact that the very fact of the interaction of language and culture is not in doubt, but how language and culture interact, for the most part remains a mystery. It is unclear what is primary in such interaction – language or culture. The very nature of the linguocultural is also incomprehensible, since linguistic and cultural phenomena have different natures and are incompatible from a philosophical point of view.

However, it can already be concluded that linguoculturology in the form in which it exists today may well exist (in a democratic society, no humanitarian studies can be banned), but it cannot be used as the basis of the RUSSIAN AS FOREIGN learning process.

Before including linguoculturology in the learning process, it is necessary to take at least two steps:

first, to clearly define the object of research; such can be the mechanisms of interaction between language and culture; secondly, to identify these mechanisms with full clarity.

If these two steps are completed, researchers will not need lengthy formulations or avoiding theoretical

contradictions, and teachers will be able to use the materials of linguoculturology in the process of teaching Russian to foreign students.

It should be mentioned that modern linguoculturology has a number of directions:

- theoretical linguoculturology;
- comparative linguoculturology;
- historical linguoculturology;
- comparative linguoculturology;
- linguoculturology of social groups;
- linguoculturology of the text;
- cognitive linguoculturology;
- geolinguoculturology;
- applied linguoculturology.

Of all these areas, we are most interested in applied linguoculturology, the main thing for which is the solution of specific methodological tasks, the search for materials for the teaching process, methods for analyzing intermediate and final results of teaching, as well as the areas of application of the results obtained in the practice of teaching Russian as foreign.

The currently existing applied linguoculturology sets itself ambitious tasks.

On the one hand, applied linguoculturology explores the problems of interaction between language and culture, existing as a theoretical discipline. At the same time, in applied linguoculturology, as well as linguoculturology in general, there is a lack of understanding of the essence of such interaction. No teacher will be able to characterize with complete clarity the mechanisms of interaction between language and culture. In other words, the theoretical basis of applied linguoculturology is illusory, being reduced to unclear formulations.

On the other hand, applied linguoculturology exists as an important aspect of linguodidactics. Russian literature focuses the students' attention on the complex of cultural values of the Russian people, claims to be a comprehensive disclosure of the linguoculturological essence of social and cultural phenomena in modern Russian society, declares the possibility of a comprehensive linguoculturological analysis of texts in Russian in a foreign audience [Vasilyuk, 2010]. However, the question arises whether it is possible to perform all these tasks with unresolved fundamental theoretical problems of linguoculturology? Probably impossible.

According to our view, the main problem of applied linguoculturology is that the materials of theoretical linguoculturology are introduced into the process of teaching a foreign language – the most controversial area, an area with an unsettled terminology, an area that not only students but also linguoculturologists themselves cannot understand. It would not be an exaggeration to say that modern theoretical linguoculturology is balancing on the edge of scientific exoticism, provocation and pseudoscience. This is the most controversial trend in modern Russian studies.

In this regard, it is not entirely clear how the results of such a direction (at the same time, extremely individualized results) can take place in the educational process?

At the same time, the idea of studying cultural realities together with language learning is productive and cannot be doubted. Russian is not a new idea and is being solved within the framework of an understandable direction in linguodidactics – within the framework of

linguistics, which does not pretend to resolve complex theoretical issues and focuses on familiarizing students with the realities of Russian culture together with teaching the Russian language [Vereshchagin, Kostomarov, 1983].

Students well assimilate the idea that each language at the lexical level reflects the spiritual and material culture of the people – the native speaker of this language. At the same time, a certain language as a communicative system does not necessarily correspond to a certain ethnic culture. The world knows many examples when people lost their ethnic language, switched to another language, even changed the language twice, but retained their ethnic culture. For example, the Jewish people, who lost their language, adopted other languages as their native languages, including Russian. However, the Jews remained Jews, developing together with other nations. The same can be said about the Komi, Permians, and many other peoples. In general, language is a communication system. Almost any cultural phenomenon can be transmitted in any developed language. For example, there is no such cultural phenomenon in Germany that cannot be conveyed in Russian. Another thing is that there is a specific national vocabulary tied to certain cultural events. However, it is easily replaced by another vocabulary. In this sense, even the etymology of the word in the process of communication does not carry a cultural meaning. When we say "Hello!", we mean a traditional greeting at a meeting, and not a wish for health.

In other words, in the process of teaching Russian As Foreign, one should not speak in little-understood words about some non-existent mystical cultural meanings

allegedly contained in the Russian language.

Russian Russian should be understood that knowledge of the vocabulary and grammar of the Russian language is not enough to fully communicate with Russian people. Russian Russian culture, of course, the deeper the student learns about Russian culture, the easier it will be for him to go through the process of communication in Russian. At the same time, he does not have to tell about concepts, linguoculturemes and many other things from modern linguoculturology, which most likely does not exist, and in Russian culture does not exist for sure.

Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to preserve the linguo-regional approach that has become a classic in teaching Russian as foreign. It is productive, understandable to teachers and students, it is justified by theory and practice. It is obvious that the appeal to the problem of learning language and culture at the same time is not accidental, since it allows us to successfully combine elements of regional studies with linguistic phenomena that act not only as a means of communication, but also as a way to familiarize students with a new reality for them. "Such an approach to teaching a foreign language in many ways provides not only a more effective solution to practical, general educational, developmental and educational tasks, but also contains huge opportunities for challenging and further maintaining the motivation of learning" [Salanovich, 1995: 9].

In any case, it will be possible to turn to applied linguoculturology as an innovation in the teaching methodology of the Russian as foreign only after solving the question of

the mechanisms of interaction between language and culture.

Results:

1. The theoretical basis of modern applied linguoculturology is theoretical linguoculturology, within which the problem of the mechanisms of interaction between language and culture is not solved. This is the main problem of applied linguoculturology. The essence of the problem is to include in the process of teaching the language questionable from

the point of view of science, unsettled conclusions.

2. These facts should be excluded from the process of teaching Russian as foreign.

3. It is possible to convey to students the cultural specifics of Russia within the framework of the traditional direction in linguodidactics – linguistics. To date, linguistics should be recognized as a priority direction in the teaching methodology of the Russian as foreign.

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